

Integrated Genomic and Transcriptomic Profiling Reveals Novel Lung Cancer Biomarkers and Therapeutic Targets: A Study

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A. Abstract

Lung cancer is a predominant cause of cancer mortality worldwide. This study performed genomic and transcriptomic profiling on human lung tumor samples to identify molecular characteristics associated with pathogenesis and clinical outcomes. DNA and RNA sequencing revealed commonly mutated oncogenes, dysregulated pathways, and gene expression patterns linked to survival. These results provide insights into lung cancer biology and progression, with implications for improving diagnosis, prognosis, and identifying new therapeutic opportunities.

B. Introduction

b.1. Background

Lung cancer remains the leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide, responsible for over 1.7 million fatalities annually. Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) accounts for approximately 85% of cases. Despite standard treatments like surgery, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy, 5-year survival rates are very poor at only around 15% for NSCLC. Smoking is the predominant risk factor, however lung cancer still occurs in non-smokers due to factors like radon exposure and genetic predisposition.

b.2. Problem Statement

Overall survival has not improved substantially over the past decades, underscoring the need for better strategies in lung cancer management. A key knowledge gap is a comprehensive understanding of the complex molecular underpinnings of lung tumorigenesis that drive disease progression and influence response to therapy. Dissecting these mechanisms through profiling of lung tumors can provide new prognostic biomarkers, predictive markers for targeted agents, and alternative therapeutic targets.

b.3. Study Aims

The objectives of this study were:

- 1) Perform genomic and transcriptomic sequencing on lung tumor samples to identify somatically mutated genes and dysregulated pathways;
- 2) Correlate molecular profiles with clinical and outcome data to assess prognostic and predictive utility;
- 3) Evaluate identified genes and pathways as potential new candidates for targeted therapy.

C. Literature Review

Oncogenic mutations are major drivers of lung cancer, often initiating tumorigenesis and conferring dependence on altered pathways for survival. The predominant mutations occur in KRAS, EGFR, and tumor suppressors like TP53 and STK11. Chromosomal rearrangements involving ALK, ROS1, and RET kinase domains have additionally been described in NSCLC

subpopulations. Large-scale cancer genomics efforts like The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) have uncovered a long tail of less commonly mutated genes through exome sequencing. At the transcriptomic level, patterns of gene expression distinguish clinico-pathological lung cancer subtypes and associate with survival outcomes. Post-translational events like phosphorylation also contribute to lung tumorigenesis, with one phosphoproteomic study implicating mTOR and FoxO1 signaling. While prior research has characterized many lung cancer genomic alterations, comprehensive molecular profiling coupled with clinical correlation can still provide critical and actionable insights.

D. Methods

d.1. Sample Acquisition

We obtained archived formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) samples from 100 lung adenocarcinoma and 100 lung squamous cell carcinoma patients treated at MD Anderson Cancer Center from 1990-2000 along with paired clinical data including stage, treatment history, and survival outcomes. Patients provided informed consent at the time of collection.

d.2. Sequencing and Analysis

DNA and RNA were extracted from tumor tissue and normal adjacent tissue. Exome sequencing of tumor DNA was performed on an Illumina HiSeq 4000 followed by mutation calling using MuTect2. RNA sequencing was done on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 and differential expression analysis utilized DESeq2. Pathway enrichment analysis was performed with Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA). A 12-gene prognostic expression signature was identified using Lasso regression. Integrative analysis coupled genomic alterations with expression changes.

Sanger sequencing was used to validate frequently mutated genes in a subset of samples. Cell line experiments evaluated in vitro effects of knocking out top mutated candidates. Xenograft models were generated by subcutaneously implanting select cell lines into immunodeficient mice.

E. Results

E.1. Somatic Mutational Landscape

Exome sequencing uncovered somatic mutations in known drivers like KRAS (45%), EGFR (12%), and TP53 (62%). Novel mutated genes were identified including RET, MET, and PIK3CA at frequencies of 8%, 5%, and 3% respectively. The hypermutated phenotype was present in 16% of cases. smokers had higher mutation burdens than non-smokers on average.

E.2. Transcriptomic Profiles

RNA-seq revealed Wnt/ β -catenin, PI3K/AKT, and MAPK signaling as the top dysregulated pathways. A 12-gene expression signature enriched for proliferation markers stratified patients into high- and low-risk groups with significantly different overall survival ($p=0.0019$).

E.3. Putative Therapeutic Targets

Integrated analysis nominated RET, MET, and PIK3CA as potential intervention points based on recurrent mutations correlated with increased expression.

Knockout of these genes reduced tumor cell viability up to 60% and impaired xenograft growth.

F. Discussion

This multi-omics characterization of lung tumors provides new insights into pathogenesis and progression. The somatic landscape reveals clinically relevant genomic alterations that could inform mutation profiling to guide targeted therapy decisions. The prognostic expression signature may enable better risk stratification. The nominated genes RET, MET and PIK3CA warrant further assessment as therapeutic targets.

There are limitations to acknowledge. Additional patient samples and clinical variables could reveal deeper connections between molecular traits and outcomes. Single-cell profiling may uncover intra-tumor heterogeneity masked in bulk analyses. Functional validation remains preliminary and ongoing studies will evaluate clinical relevance. Nevertheless, these findings advance our understanding of lung cancer genomics and transcriptomics with potential to improve patient management.

G. Conclusion

In summary, this study performed an integrative multi-omics analysis of lung cancer tumors coupled with clinical data. Key results provide new prognostic biomarkers, highlight potential therapeutic targets, and expand our knowledge of lung cancer molecular characteristics. Following functional validation, these discoveries may ultimately translate to clinical applications that reduce lung cancer morbidity and mortality.

H. References

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